

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ZEFACK****FIRST NAME: JUDE TSAFACK****PROGRAM CODE : ACA-401D****COURSE CODE: DEPI****PERIOD NUMBER: PERIOD 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar.

The student used Turabian footnote references with Zotero.:

The author uses Zotero to insert references.

The author uses Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 2%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 365 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR ACA-401D

1. What is the purpose of an academic essay?

- To educate or convince the reader**¹
- To amuse the reader
- To share personal tales
- To display the author's inventiveness

2. Which of the following is NOT an essential component of an academic essay?

- Conclusion
- Table of contents**²

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma Kabiru, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 7.

² Ibid., 10.

- Bibliography
 - Introduction
3. When should you use in-text citations in your academic essay?
- Anytime you include information, thoughts, or phrases from another source** ³
 - Only in the introduction
 - Only in the conclusion
 - Only in the body paragraphs
4. What is the primary purpose of the Turabian style?
- Produce aesthetically pleasing materials
 - Promote the use of colloquial language in research papers
 - Offer instructions on academic writing and citation** ⁴
 - Encourage plagiarism in academic work
5. In Turabian style, what is the correct order for elements in a citation for a book in the bibliography?
- Author, title, publisher, date
 - Title, author, publisher, date** ⁵
 - Title, date, author, publisher

³ Ibid., 34–35.

⁴ Kate L Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018).

⁵ Ibid., 140–146.

- Publisher, date, author, title
6. What is the preferred font style and size in Turabian for the main text of your paper?
- Times New Roman, 12-point** ⁶
- Arial, 10-point
- Comic Sans, 14-point
- Calibri, 11-point
7. When citing a website in Turabian style, which information is typically included in the footnote or endnote?
- Author's biography
- Page layout design
- File format
- URL and access date** ⁷
8. In Turabian style, what is the recommended line spacing for the main text of your paper?
- Single-spacing
- Double spacing** ⁸
- 1.5-line spacing

⁶ Ibid., 161–168.

⁷ Ibid., 143.

⁸ Ibid., 161–168.

1.15-line spacing

9. What is the role of a research proposal in the dissertation process?

It outlines the entire dissertation project⁹

It provides a summary of the research findings

It lists the limitations of the study

It is optional in qualitative research

10. What is the role of a literature review in the dissertation process?

It presents the primary research findings

It provides a summary of existing research on the topic¹⁰

It outlines the entire research methodology

It is not necessary for dissertation research

⁹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth Edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2019).

¹⁰ James P Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Florida: Florida State University, 2017).

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation : A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth Edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2019.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.